

Appendix A: Supplementary data

Figure A.1 presents the comparison in the low atmosphere for the two correction methods used to reconstruct the correct counts at m/z 28 (where the signal at this m/z is saturated) from the raw counts (black curve), using as a proxy either m/z 14 (yellow curve) as in Niemann et al. (2010) or m/z 29 (blue curve) as in the present work. While both methods introduce the same order of magnitude correction to channel 28, the one we used based on m/z 29 induces a slightly lower intensity for this channel. A correction using mass 14 propagates errors from the contribution of the methane fragment, while one on mass 29 propagate errors from the contribution of the ethane fragment. Given the much higher mole fraction of methane, subsequent errors are expected to be higher using mass 14 than using mass 29. See an illustration of this effect in Figure A.3 comparing the normalized raw counts ratios of mass 14 to mass 28 and mass 29 to mass 28 for very high-altitude data obtained using the leak 2, in the 145-70 km range. It is clear in this figure that the ration between masses 14 and 28 presents. On the other hand, the 29/28 ratio remains almost exactly constant allowing to properly characterize the nitrogen contribution at mass 29 and then use it as a proxy for low altitude saturated peaks. However, while we believe mass 29 correction to be slightly better, we do note that the improvement on the mass 28 correction is small and we clearly consider that any previous work based on the data using mass 14 as a proxy for correcting nitrogen signal should still be considered solid.

The difference between both calibration is mainly visible at high saturation values, after Huygens touchdown visible on Figure A.1 after 8,000 seconds.

Fig. A.1. Channel 28 intensity (in counts per seconds) in the GCMS data versus time since the beginning of GCMS sequence for the measurements in the lower part of the atmosphere (below 30 km) and at the surface of Titan. Black curve is the raw count currently reported in the level 2 archived product; yellow curve is the reconstructed count using the same method as Niemann et al. 2010 and channel 14 as a proxy; and blue curve is the reconstructed count used in this work, based on m/z 29. Huygens touchdown on Titan’s surface is visible in the data as the flattening of the profile occurring after 8000 seconds.

The entire set of recalibrated GCMS data is provided as a separate file and includes the GCMS level 3 data product generated during this work. Following the nomenclature of the GCMS data archived on the PDS this file is named *GCMS_IUS_STG3.TAB*.

The associated file *GCMS_IUS_STG3.FMT* contains a description of each column following the existing archived format. An additional information in the description “Modified between STG2 and STG3” indicates

Table A1 presents the retrieved methane mixing ratio through the atmospheric column and Table A2 presents the initial fragmentation database used to seed the Monte-Carlo sampling and

Fig. A.2. Comparison of channel 14 to channel 28 (upper) and channel 29 to channel 28 (lower) ratios for high altitude data acquired through leak 2 between 145 and 70km together with their respective linear fits. To emphasize trends, ratios were normalized to the mean of the ratios in the 70-145km altitude range

Fig. A.3. Ratio of the raw counts of mass 16 to mass 28 in the 70km to 30 km altitude range. Background color indicates reliability of data. Green is for data without reliability concerns, for altitudes from 145 km to 65km and then from 40km down to the surface for sampling through leak 1 and leak 2 respectively. Red is for data we know for sure should not be used for methane profile from 65 km to 55km. These data correspond to atmospheric sampling made through another leak (leak 3, not discussed in this paper) for rare gas and enrichment cells experiments, as well as an altitude range where a GCMS pump stall is suspected. The very low end of this area shows a rapid decay in the I_{16}/I_{18} ratio likely related to filament outgassing. The last area, in orange, corresponds to altitudes between 55 and 40km, for which data quality is harder to assess.

Fig. A.4. Bin size used in Niemann et al. 2010 for vertical stacking as a function of altitude. These bin sizes were reconstructed using the average value presented in Niemann et al. 2010 for pressure and temperature and the required number of points necessary to obtain such averages

Fig. A.5. Reverse-engineered $Cf_{16,28}$ factor used in Niemann et al. 2010 (blue triangle, with their associated errorbars), compared to our analytical proxy calculated as described in section 2 (dashed red line), as a function of altitude.

Table A1. Retrieved methane mole fractions through the atmosphere of Titan.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
65.2	146	2.9	166.4	1.24	0.02
81.6	145.2	2.9	165.1	1.32	0.02
100.3	144.2	2.9	164.4	1.35	0.02
119.1	143.4	3	163.7	1.23	0.02
135.5	142.2	3.1	162.9	1.32	0.02
157	141.2	3.2	162.4	1.31	0.02
178	140.2	3.3	161.8	1.38	0.02
199.1	139.3	3.3	161.3	1.35	0.02
217.8	138.2	3.4	160.9	1.36	0.02
237.7	137.3	3.5	160.9	1.38	0.02
258.2	136.1	3.6	160.4	1.38	0.02
279.2	135.2	3.7	160	1.41	0.02
300.2	134.1	3.8	159.8	1.4	0.02
323.5	133.2	3.9	159.9	1.37	0.02
344.5	132.2	4	160.2	1.41	0.02
365.7	131.2	4.1	159.7	1.38	0.02
389.3	130.2	4.2	157.7	1.42	0.02
412.7	129.2	4.4	156.4	1.4	0.02
436	128.2	4.4	156.1	1.42	0.02
460.8	127.2	4.6	156.2	1.4	0.02
483.1	126.2	4.7	156	1.42	0.02
506.5	125.2	4.8	155.2	1.37	0.02
529.8	124.2	5	155.2	1.45	0.02
555.5	123.2	5.1	155.3	1.41	0.02
580.1	122.2	5.2	155.5	1.42	0.02
605	121.1	5.4	155.1	1.39	0.02
630.6	120.2	5.5	155.5	1.45	0.02
658.6	119.2	5.7	155.5	1.43	0.02
687.1	118.2	5.8	154.2	1.42	0.02
710.4	117.4	6	153.5	1.41	0.02
738.4	116.2	6.2	153.4	1.4	0.02
766.4	115.2	6.3	153.5	1.41	0.02
792.1	114.2	6.5	153.2	1.42	0.02
823.2	113.3	6.7	151.6	1.39	0.02
851.2	112.1	6.9	150.3	1.42	0.02
879	111.3	6.8	148.8	1.42	0.02
909.8	110.3	6.9	147.6	1.44	0.02
930.8	108.8	7.1	146.6	1.43	0.03
947.1	108.2	7.2	146.2	1.44	0.03
961	107.2	7.4	146	1.42	0.02
975	106.2	7.7	146.2	1.45	0.02
989	105.3	7.9	145.1	1.4	0.02
1003	104.5	8.1	143.7	1.42	0.02
1017	103.1	8.5	143.2	1.42	0.02
1033.9	102.2	8.8	143.1	1.44	0.03
1043.2	101.2	9.1	143	1.46	0.02
1057.2	100.2	9.3	142.6	1.37	0.02
1073.5	99.2	9.6	141.4	1.46	0.03
1087.6	98.2	9.9	141.4	1.44	0.02
1101.6	97.2	10.2	141.4	1.41	0.02
1115.8	96.4	10.5	140.7	1.32	0.03
1130	95	11	140	1.43	0.02
1146.3	94.2	11.3	139	1.5	0.03
1162.7	93.3	11.6	137.9	1.44	0.03
1176.6	92.3	12	137.4	1.44	0.03
1192.9	91.2	12.3	137.2	1.43	0.02
1211.6	90.2	12.8	137	1.43	0.02
1227.9	89.2	13.2	136.3	1.4	0.02
1243.6	88	13.7	135.6	1.47	0.03
1263.3	87.1	14.2	134	1.42	0.02
1279.6	86.2	14.5	132.8	1.44	0.03

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
1295.9	85.2	15	132.4	1.45	0.02
1314.5	84.2	15.6	131.3	1.43	0.02
1332.5	83.2	16.1	129.9	1.42	0.02
1354.6	82.4	16.6	128.5	1.45	0.02
1375.6	81.1	17.3	127.8	1.43	0.03
1394.1	80.2	17.9	126.9	1.44	0.02
1414.9	79.2	18.5	125.1	1.45	0.02
1435.8	78.3	19.1	123.9	1.45	0.03
1454.4	77.2	19.9	121.8	1.46	0.03
1480.7	76.1	20.7	120.2	1.44	0.02
1503.6	75.2	21.4	118	1.45	0.03
1526.6	74.3	22.1	116.9	1.46	0.02
1548.7	73.2	23.1	115.4	-	-
1575.7	72.2	24	113.5	-	-
1601	71.2	25	110.8	-	-
1626.5	70.2	26	106.4	-	-
1654.2	69.2	27.2	104.4	-	-
1681.7	68.3	28.3	102.1	-	-
1710.1	67.3	29.6	98.5	-	-
1740	66.2	31.2	94.3	-	-
1772.5	65.2	32.8	90.6	-	-
1804.8	64.2	34.5	86.9	-	-
1839.1	63	36.9	82.9	-	-
1875.8	62.2	38.5	80.3	-	-
1914.6	61.2	40.8	78	-	-
1954.3	60.2	43.2	76.8	-	-
1994.1	59.2	45.9	75.3	-	-
2037.3	58.2	48.6	74.6	-	-
2083	57.1	51.8	73.6	-	-
2130.5	56.2	54.8	72.8	-	-
2175.2	55.3	58	72.4	2.32	0.03
2225.7	54.2	62	71.8	2.05	0.03
2274.3	53.2	65.9	71.4	1.99	0.03
2326.3	52.3	69.7	71.2	1.91	0.03
2382.2	51.2	74.7	71	1.88	0.03
2439.1	50.1	79.8	70.8	1.64	0.03
2494.9	49.3	84.2	70.8	1.86	0.03
2555	48.2	90.3	70.5	1.75	0.03
2615.1	47.2	95.9	70.5	1.71	0.02
2681.2	46.1	102.8	70.4	1.73	0.03
2743.7	45.2	108.6	70.4	1.62	0.03
2816.7	44.1	116.2	70.4	1.63	0.03
2888.1	43.3	122.3	70.4	1.65	0.03
2955.2	42.2	131.3	70.4	1.67	0.03
3030.6	41.2	139.8	70.4	1.45	0.03
3108.9	40.2	148.5	70.5	1.64	0.03
3188.6	39.2	158.8	70.6	1.65	0.03
3268.7	38.2	168.5	70.6	1.56	0.03
3354.7	37.3	178.5	70.7	1.69	0.03
3443.6	36.2	190.7	70.8	1.53	0.02
3533.3	35.2	203.3	71	1.66	0.03
3623.3	34.3	215.7	71.2	1.62	0.03
3718.1	33.4	228.2	71.4	1.59	0.02
3815.5	32.5	240.4	71.6	1.59	0.03
3917.2	31	255.7	71.9	1.67	0.03
4025.2	30.979	256.9	72.1	1.62	0.09
4034.6	30.886	258.3	72.1	1.62	0.09
4044.1	30.799	259.7	72.1	1.64	0.11
4053.5	30.711	261.1	72.1	1.63	0.1
4062.9	30.617	263.6	72.1	1.64	0.1
4157.9	30.4	267.5	72.2	1.64	0.1

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
4167.4	30.1	273.6	72.4	1.64	0.1
4176.9	29.7	279.8	72.6	1.65	0.1
4186.2	29.4	284.3	72.7	1.64	0.1
4214.4	29.227	286.4	72.7	1.65	0.1
4223.8	29.137	287.9	72.7	1.64	0.1
4233.2	29.057	289.4	72.7	1.66	0.1
4242.7	28.966	290.9	72.7	1.67	0.08
4252.2	28.885	292.4	72.7	1.66	0.09
4261.5	28.803	293.8	72.8	1.66	0.09
4270.9	28.715	295.3	72.8	1.65	0.1
4280.3	28.636	296.8	72.9	1.66	0.1
4289.7	28.546	298.3	72.9	1.64	0.09
4299.2	28.464	299.8	72.9	1.67	0.1
4308.5	28.379	302.5	73	1.68	0.12
4336.8	28.134	306	73.1	1.68	0.12
4346.2	28.055	307.5	73.1	1.69	0.12
4355.6	27.97	309	73.1	1.7	0.13
4365	27.892	310.5	73.1	1.71	0.13
4374.5	27.818	317.7	73.3	1.71	0.13
4451.6	27.136	325.2	73.4	1.72	0.13
4461	27.059	326.8	73.4	1.72	0.13
4470.4	26.982	328.4	73.5	1.72	0.13
4479.9	26.897	329.9	73.5	1.74	0.11
4489.2	26.818	331.5	73.6	1.75	0.1
4498.7	26.737	332.7	73.6	1.78	0.08
4508.2	26.704	333.9	73.6	1.78	0.08
4517.5	26.627	335.5	73.7	1.79	0.07
4526.9	26.541	337.1	73.7	1.79	0.08
4536.3	26.465	338.7	73.7	1.78	0.08
4545.8	26.381	341.6	73.8	1.78	0.07
4574	26.148	345.2	73.9	1.78	0.07
4583.5	26.066	346.8	73.9	1.78	0.07
4592.8	25.991	348.8	73.9	1.77	0.08
4602.3	25.917	350.9	74	1.77	0.08
4611.6	25.83	352.5	74	1.76	0.08
4621	25.758	354.1	74	1.76	0.08
4630.5	25.678	355.7	74.1	1.76	0.08
4639.8	25.601	356.8	74.1	1.78	0.09
4649.3	25.53	358.7	74.2	1.77	0.1
4658.8	25.449	360.7	74.2	1.76	0.09
4668.1	25.374	364	74.3	1.77	0.09
4696.3	25.148	367.3	74.4	1.77	0.1
4705.8	25.066	368.9	74.4	1.77	0.09
4715.1	24.994	370.6	74.5	1.78	0.1
4724.6	24.913	372.3	74.5	1.79	0.11
4734.1	24.842	373.9	74.6	1.8	0.11
4743.4	24.766	376	74.6	1.8	0.11
4760.2	24.65	378.5	74.7	1.81	0.1
4769.5	24.55	381.1	74.7	1.83	0.11
4779	24.476	382.4	74.8	1.84	0.11
4788.4	24.402	384.1	74.8	1.87	0.13
4797.8	24.327	387.1	74.9	1.88	0.13
4821.4	24.147	390.1	75	1.88	0.13
4828.8	24.082	391.4	75	1.9	0.13
4836.4	24.026	392.6	75	1.91	0.12
4843.9	23.967	394	75	1.92	0.12
4851.5	23.912	395.2	75.1	1.94	0.11
4859	23.846	397.4	75.1	1.94	0.11
4866.5	23.784	398.3	75.1	1.94	0.11
4874	23.73	399.6	75.1	1.96	0.12
4881.6	23.668	400.8	75.2	1.97	0.12

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
4889.1	23.614	402.1	75.2	1.99	0.11
4896.7	23.55	403.9	75.3	1.99	0.11
4904.2	23.497	405	75.3	1.99	0.1
4911.7	23.432	406.3	75.3	2	0.08
4919.2	23.379	409.5	75.3	2.01	0.1
4941.8	23.2	412	75.3	2.03	0.11
4949.3	23.149	413.4	75.3	2.02	0.11
4956.9	23.086	415.1	75.3	2.04	0.1
4964.4	23.035	416.8	75.4	2.04	0.1
4972	22.969	418.2	75.4	2.06	0.11
4979.5	22.919	419.5	75.5	2.06	0.11
4987	22.861	420.5	75.5	2.07	0.1
4994.5	22.798	422.2	75.5	2.07	0.1
5002.1	22.742	424	75.6	2.07	0.1
5009.6	22.683	425.3	75.6	2.07	0.11
5017.1	22.629	426.6	75.6	2.09	0.11
5024.6	22.567	427.9	75.7	2.1	0.09
5032.2	22.515	429.3	75.7	2.1	0.09
5039.7	22.453	433.2	75.8	2.11	0.08
5069.7	22.225	436.8	75.9	2.11	0.07
5077.2	22.172	438.8	75.9	2.11	0.08
5084.8	22.113	439.7	76	2.13	0.09
5092.2	22.063	441	76	2.12	0.1
5099.8	21.999	442.8	76.1	2.12	0.1
5107.3	21.947	444.7	76.1	2.11	0.1
5114.9	21.887	446	76.1	2.1	0.1
5122.4	21.836	447.3	76.2	2.1	0.1
5129.9	21.776	448.7	76.2	2.1	0.11
5137.4	21.722	450.1	76.2	2.11	0.11
5145	21.662	451.8	76.3	2.11	0.11
5152.5	21.61	453.2	76.3	2.11	0.11
5160	21.553	454.6	76.4	2.12	0.11
5167.5	21.492	457.8	76.4	2.14	0.13
5190.2	21.328	461	76.5	2.15	0.13
5197.6	21.27	462.4	76.5	2.15	0.13
5205.2	21.217	464.4	76.5	2.15	0.14
5212.7	21.161	465.3	76.5	2.14	0.13
5220.3	21.11	466.6	76.6	2.16	0.12
5227.8	21.052	468.5	76.6	2.17	0.11
5235.3	21.004	469.8	76.6	2.19	0.1
5242.8	20.943	471.3	76.6	2.19	0.1
5250.4	20.893	473.2	76.7	2.2	0.09
5257.9	20.836	474.5	76.7	2.22	0.08
5265.5	20.784	476	76.7	2.22	0.08
5272.9	20.724	477.8	76.8	2.23	0.09
5280.5	20.665	479.1	76.8	2.24	0.09
5288	20.615	482.3	76.9	2.23	0.09
5310.6	20.447	485.3	76.9	2.23	0.08
5318.1	20.398	486.7	77	2.22	0.09
5325.7	20.34	488.1	77	2.23	0.08
5333.2	20.287	490	77.1	2.23	0.09
5340.8	20.23	491.5	77.1	2.23	0.09
5348.2	20.181	492.8	77.1	2.24	0.09
5355.8	20.125	494.2	77.1	2.24	0.09
5363.3	20.075	495.7	77.2	2.25	0.09
5370.9	20.019	497.6	77.2	2.26	0.07
5378.4	19.967	499.5	77.2	2.27	0.08
5385.9	19.909	500.9	77.2	2.27	0.08
5393.4	19.861	502.4	77.3	2.28	0.09
5401	19.807	503.9	77.3	2.27	0.09
5408.5	19.757	506.5	77.3	2.26	0.08

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
5431.1	19.595	510.1	77.4	2.27	0.08
5438.6	19.538	511.6	77.4	2.28	0.09
5446.2	19.491	513	77.4	2.29	0.08
5453.7	19.435	514.9	77.5	2.3	0.08
5461.2	19.384	516.8	77.5	2.29	0.08
5468.7	19.326	518.2	77.5	2.3	0.07
5476.3	19.276	519.7	77.5	2.31	0.07
5483.8	19.216	521.2	77.6	2.31	0.07
5491.3	19.168	522.6	77.6	2.32	0.08
5498.8	19.112	524.5	77.7	2.33	0.07
5506.4	19.065	526.1	77.7	2.31	0.07
5513.9	19.007	527.6	77.7	2.32	0.07
5521.5	18.959	529.6	77.7	2.31	0.07
5529	18.905	533.1	77.8	2.33	0.07
5551.6	18.745	536	77.9	2.35	0.09
5559.1	18.695	537.5	77.9	2.36	0.09
5566.6	18.638	539.5	78	2.35	0.09
5574.1	18.589	541	78	2.36	0.09
5581.7	18.534	542.4	78	2.35	0.09
5589.2	18.486	544.4	78.1	2.36	0.1
5596.8	18.432	545.8	78.1	2.36	0.1
5604.2	18.382	547.4	78.2	2.36	0.1
5611.8	18.328	549.3	78.2	2.35	0.11
5619.3	18.279	550.8	78.2	2.36	0.11
5626.9	18.223	552.4	78.3	2.36	0.11
5634.4	18.176	553.8	78.3	2.37	0.1
5641.9	18.12	555.5	78.3	2.38	0.1
5649.4	18.07	559	78.4	2.39	0.11
5672	17.916	562.5	78.5	2.38	0.11
5679.5	17.862	564.1	78.5	2.37	0.09
5687.1	17.815	565.6	78.5	2.37	0.09
5694.6	17.758	567.6	78.6	2.38	0.1
5702.2	17.711	569.2	78.6	2.39	0.1
5709.7	17.658	570.7	78.6	2.41	0.09
5717.2	17.609	572.1	78.7	2.4	0.09
5724.7	17.555	574.3	78.7	2.42	0.1
5732.3	17.509	575.8	78.8	2.43	0.11
5739.8	17.455	577.4	78.8	2.44	0.09
5747.3	17.409	578.9	78.8	2.44	0.1
5754.8	17.353	580.9	78.8	2.45	0.1
5762.4	17.306	582.9	78.9	2.46	0.1
5769.9	17.254	586.5	78.9	2.48	0.11
5792.5	17.097	589.6	79	2.49	0.11
5800	17.051	591.1	79	2.51	0.1
5807.6	16.998	593.2	79	2.52	0.1
5815.1	16.949	594.7	79.1	2.53	0.11
5822.6	16.897	596.3	79.1	2.55	0.12
5830.1	16.849	598.3	79.1	2.56	0.12
5837.7	16.795	599.9	79.2	2.57	0.12
5845.2	16.749	601	79.2	2.59	0.11
5852.8	16.694	603.2	79.2	2.6	0.12
5860.2	16.645	604.7	79.3	2.61	0.13
5867.8	16.595	606.8	79.3	2.64	0.1
5875.3	16.547	608.4	79.3	2.67	0.09
5882.9	16.496	610	79.4	2.69	0.09
5890.4	16.449	613.7	79.4	2.71	0.09
5913	16.297	617.4	79.5	2.72	0.09
5920.5	16.25	619.5	79.6	2.73	0.08
5928.1	16.196	633.4	79.8	2.74	0.08
6032.5	15.514	646.2	80	2.74	0.07
6041.9	15.455	648.4	80	2.73	0.11

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
6051.3	15.399	650.5	80.1	2.75	0.15
6060.8	15.333	653.4	80.1	2.76	0.15
6070.2	15.275	654.9	80.2	2.78	0.15
6079.6	15.209	657.1	80.2	2.8	0.15
6089.1	15.151	659.3	80.2	2.8	0.15
6098.4	15.092	661.4	80.3	2.81	0.15
6107.8	15.029	667.4	80.4	2.82	0.15
6193.5	14.75	677.9	80.6	2.82	0.15
6202.9	14.5	685	80.7	2.82	0.15
6212.3	14.368	688.8	80.8	2.83	0.16
6221.7	14.304	691.1	80.8	2.84	0.16
6231.1	14.248	693.9	80.9	2.87	0.18
6240.6	14.187	696.6	81	2.88	0.18
6249.9	14.131	700.5	81	2.9	0.17
6278.2	13.956	705.6	81.1	2.95	0.11
6287.6	13.894	707.8	81.1	2.96	0.12
6297	13.837	710	81.1	2.98	0.14
6306.4	13.786	712.3	81.2	3.01	0.16
6315.9	13.723	714.4	81.2	2.99	0.17
6325.3	13.667	716.7	81.3	3.03	0.19
6334.7	13.604	718.9	81.3	3.03	0.19
6344	13.549	721.2	81.3	3.07	0.22
6353.5	13.495	723.4	81.4	3.13	0.25
6362.9	13.434	726.3	81.4	3.16	0.24
6372.3	13.378	728.6	81.5	3.18	0.24
6381.7	13.3	730.9	81.5	3.19	0.23
6391.2	13.26	733.1	81.5	3.23	0.27
6400.5	13.198	735.9	81.6	3.26	0.26
6410	13.142	749.2	81.8	3.29	0.25
6513.5	12.519	763.4	82.1	3.34	0.29
6521	12.468	765.6	82.2	3.39	0.32
6528.6	12.419	767.4	82.2	3.4	0.31
6536	12.377	769.1	82.2	3.39	0.32
6543.6	12.33	771.4	82.2	3.48	0.28
6551.1	12.288	773.1	82.3	3.51	0.3
6558.7	12.239	774.8	82.3	3.58	0.29
6566.2	12.194	777.1	82.4	3.6	0.29
6573.8	12.146	778.9	82.4	3.61	0.29
6581.3	12.104	780.7	82.4	3.61	0.28
6588.8	12.056	783	82.4	3.64	0.28
6596.3	12.015	784.8	82.4	3.68	0.25
6603.9	11.967	786.5	82.5	3.68	0.25
6611.3	11.923	790.7	82.5	3.7	0.24
6634	11.786	794.8	82.5	3.73	0.23
6641.5	11.746	797.1	82.6	3.74	0.25
6649	11.695	798.8	82.6	3.75	0.25
6656.5	11.648	800.7	82.6	3.78	0.23
6664.1	11.606	803	82.7	3.8	0.2
6671.6	11.559	804.7	82.7	3.8	0.2
6679.2	11.517	806.5	82.8	3.78	0.2
6686.6	11.471	808.9	82.8	3.76	0.2
6694.2	11.431	810.7	82.8	3.76	0.19
6701.7	11.381	815	82.9	3.74	0.22
6724.3	11.251	818.5	83	3.78	0.2
6731.8	11.204	822.7	83.1	3.77	0.2
6754.5	11.075	826.8	83.2	3.77	0.2
6762	11.028	828.6	83.2	3.75	0.23
6769.5	10.981	830.4	83.2	3.75	0.23
6777	10.939	832.7	83.2	3.77	0.25
6784.6	10.893	834.6	83.3	3.75	0.23
6792.1	10.852	836.5	83.3	3.71	0.23

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
6799.7	10.805	838.9	83.4	3.71	0.23
6807.1	10.764	840.7	83.4	3.73	0.22
6814.7	10.718	842.5	83.4	3.72	0.21
6822.2	10.676	844.9	83.4	3.73	0.21
6829.8	10.63	847.8	83.5	3.77	0.24
6844.6	10.55	850.9	83.5	3.75	0.24
6852.2	10.504	852.7	83.5	3.79	0.23
6859.7	10.457	856.3	83.6	3.81	0.25
6882.3	10.328	860.5	83.7	3.84	0.25
6889.7	10.283	862.9	83.7	3.86	0.27
6897.3	10.243	864.7	83.7	3.92	0.23
6904.8	10.196	866.5	83.8	3.93	0.23
6912.4	10.156	869.7	83.8	3.91	0.22
6919.9	10.11	871	83.9	3.94	0.24
6927.5	10.069	872.8	83.9	3.99	0.21
6935	10.021	875.2	83.9	4.03	0.21
6942.5	9.974	877	84	4.07	0.23
6950	9.934	878.9	84	4.07	0.22
6957.6	9.888	881.3	84	4.1	0.22
6965.1	9.847	883.8	84.1	4.1	0.22
6972.7	9.8	885.8	84.1	4.14	0.17
6980.2	9.76	888.8	84.1	4.15	0.17
7002.8	9.628	894	84.2	4.15	0.17
7010.3	9.588	896.5	84.3	4.17	0.17
7017.8	9.544	898.4	84.3	4.14	0.2
7025.3	9.504	900.2	84.3	4.11	0.21
7032.9	9.458	902.1	84.3	4.14	0.2
7040.4	9.419	903.9	84.3	4.16	0.19
7048	9.373	906.4	84.3	4.16	0.19
7055.4	9.334	908.8	84.4	4.19	0.24
7063	9.289	910.7	84.4	4.22	0.29
7070.5	9.244	912.5	84.5	4.24	0.3
7078.1	9.204	915	84.5	4.27	0.28
7085.6	9.157	916.9	84.5	4.27	0.28
7093.2	9.117	918.7	84.6	4.31	0.32
7100.6	9.072	923.1	84.6	4.34	0.33
7123.3	8.949	928.4	84.7	4.37	0.34
7130.8	8.905	929.7	84.7	4.38	0.34
7138.3	8.863	932.2	84.8	4.39	0.33
7153.2	8.8	935.3	84.8	4.43	0.29
7160.7	8.735	937.8	84.9	4.49	0.25
7168.2	8.697	940.4	84.9	4.53	0.24
7175.8	8.652	942.2	85	4.54	0.23
7183.3	8.614	944.2	85	4.57	0.22
7190.8	8.569	946.7	85	4.61	0.29
7198.3	8.53	948.5	85	4.61	0.3
7205.9	8.485	949.8	85.1	4.61	0.3
7213.4	8.447	953.1	85.1	4.66	0.3
7221	8.401	955	85.1	4.72	0.3
7228.5	8.361	958.9	85.2	4.71	0.29
7251.1	8.234	963.4	85.3	4.74	0.3
7258.6	8.19	966	85.4	4.73	0.3
7266.1	8.152	968.5	85.4	4.77	0.29
7273.6	8.106	970.4	85.4	4.8	0.26
7281.2	8.067	972.3	85.5	4.83	0.24
7288.7	8.022	974.9	85.5	4.9	0.35
7296.3	7.983	976.8	85.5	4.89	0.35
7303.8	7.939	978.8	85.5	4.96	0.33
7311.3	7.902	981.4	85.6	4.95	0.34
7318.8	7.857	983.4	85.6	4.94	0.33
7326.4	7.818	985.3	85.6	4.95	0.33

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
7333.9	7.773	987.7	85.7	4.98	0.32
7341.5	7.735	989.4	85.7	4.98	0.32
7348.9	7.69	994	85.8	4.97	0.32
7371.6	7.564	998.5	85.8	4.97	0.32
7379	7.525	1001.2	85.8	4.97	0.32
7386.6	7.482	1003.1	85.9	5.02	0.32
7394.1	7.444	1005.1	85.9	5.02	0.32
7401.7	7.399	1007.7	86	5.04	0.31
7409.2	7.362	1009.7	86	5.06	0.32
7416.7	7.318	1011	86	5.04	0.27
7424.2	7.279	1014.5	86.1	5.08	0.24
7431.8	7.236	1016.5	86.1	5.08	0.24
7439.3	7.197	1018.4	86.2	5.14	0.22
7446.8	7.155	1021.1	86.2	5.1	0.25
7461.7	7.1	1024.4	86.3	5.11	0.25
7469.3	7.034	1027.7	86.4	5.09	0.27
7476.8	6.99	1034.4	86.5	5.1	0.27
7514.4	6.8	1041	86.6	5.08	0.28
7521.9	6.749	1042.9	86.6	5.09	0.26
7529.5	6.711	1045	86.6	5.09	0.27
7537	6.668	1047.6	86.6	5.1	0.29
7544.5	6.625	1049.8	86.7	5.11	0.29
7552	6.587	1051.8	86.7	5.14	0.3
7559.6	6.545	1053.8	86.8	5.11	0.31
7567.1	6.508	1055.8	86.8	5.07	0.31
7574.7	6.464	1058.5	86.9	5.04	0.31
7582.2	6.425	1061.1	86.9	5.04	0.31
7589.7	6.383	1063.2	87	5.02	0.29
7597.2	6.346	1067.2	87	5.08	0.3
7619.8	6.224	1072	87.1	5.08	0.3
7627.3	6.187	1074	87.2	5.1	0.29
7634.9	6.143	1076.8	87.2	5.11	0.3
7642.4	6.106	1078.9	87.2	5.15	0.29
7650	6.064	1080.9	87.2	5.21	0.31
7657.5	6.026	1083	87.3	5.25	0.3
7665	5.984	1085.6	87.3	5.21	0.3
7672.5	5.941	1088.3	87.3	5.22	0.3
7680.1	5.903	1090.4	87.4	5.22	0.3
7687.6	5.861	1092.4	87.4	5.26	0.28
7695.1	5.824	1095.2	87.5	5.25	0.3
7702.6	5.782	1097.3	87.5	5.28	0.27
7710.2	5.745	1099.3	87.5	5.28	0.27
7717.7	5.703	1104	87.6	5.31	0.28
7740.3	5.589	1108	87.7	5.28	0.28
7747.8	5.548	1110.8	87.7	5.29	0.28
7755.4	5.5	1115.8	87.8	5.3	0.26
7770.3	5.42	1117.8	87.8	5.3	0.26
7777.8	5.388	1119.9	87.9	5.28	0.28
7785.3	5.352	1121.9	87.9	5.24	0.25
7792.9	5.311	1124.1	87.9	5.23	0.24
7800.3	5.274	1126.8	88	5.24	0.23
7807.9	5.234	1128.8	88	5.24	0.24
7815.4	5.197	1130.9	88	5.26	0.25
7823	5.156	1132.9	88.1	5.27	0.27
7830.5	5.12	1134.9	88.1	5.29	0.24
7838	5.079	1137.7	88.1	5.31	0.25
7845.5	5.037	1143.3	88.2	5.33	0.25
7868.2	4.925	1146.8	88.3	5.33	0.25
7875.6	4.884	1148.9	88.3	5.35	0.25
7883.2	4.848	1151.6	88.3	5.37	0.26
7890.7	4.807	1153.7	88.4	5.38	0.25

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
7898.3	4.772	1155.7	88.4	5.4	0.26
7905.8	4.731	1158.5	88.5	5.43	0.22
7913.3	4.693	1160.5	88.5	5.42	0.24
7920.8	4.653	1162.6	88.5	5.43	0.24
7928.4	4.617	1165.4	88.6	5.43	0.23
7935.9	4.576	1167.4	88.6	5.47	0.28
7943.5	4.54	1169.5	88.6	5.5	0.3
7951	4.499	1172.3	88.6	5.49	0.3
7958.5	4.459	1174.4	88.7	5.54	0.24
7966	4.423	1178.7	88.7	5.55	0.25
7988.6	4.306	1183.7	88.8	5.55	0.25
7996.1	4.269	1186.5	88.9	5.56	0.25
8003.7	4.229	1188.6	88.9	5.59	0.28
8011.2	4.192	1190.7	88.9	5.6	0.28
8018.8	4.151	1192.9	89	5.61	0.28
8026.3	4.115	1195	89	5.58	0.29
8033.8	4.075	1197.8	89	5.59	0.29
8041.3	4.04	1200.6	89.1	5.63	0.25
8048.9	3.999	1202.6	89.1	5.63	0.25
8056.4	3.964	1204.1	89.1	5.64	0.24
8063.9	3.923	1209.2	89.2	5.61	0.21
8082.5	3.827	1212.8	89.3	5.57	0.19
8090.1	3.791	1214.9	89.3	5.56	0.2
8097.6	3.751	1219.9	89.4	5.54	0.21
8120.2	3.641	1224.8	89.5	5.54	0.21
8127.7	3.6	1227.7	89.6	5.53	0.22
8135.3	3.56	1229.8	89.6	5.53	0.22
8142.8	3.525	1232	89.6	5.51	0.19
8150.3	3.489	1234.1	89.7	5.52	0.19
8157.8	3.449	1236.3	89.7	5.51	0.19
8165.4	3.414	1239.2	89.7	5.52	0.18
8172.9	3.373	1241.3	89.8	5.54	0.2
8180.5	3.338	1243.5	89.8	5.53	0.2
8187.9	3.297	1247.3	89.9	5.53	0.2
8195.5	3.258	1248.7	89.9	5.54	0.19
8203	3.223	1250.8	89.9	5.55	0.19
8210.6	3.183	1253.7	89.9	5.58	0.21
8218.1	3.149	1258.6	90	5.58	0.22
8240.7	3.035	1262.9	90.1	5.58	0.22
8248.2	3	1265.1	90.1	5.56	0.22
8255.7	2.96	1268	90.1	5.58	0.21
8263.2	2.923	1270.2	90.2	5.57	0.21
8270.8	2.884	1271.7	90.2	5.57	0.2
8278.3	2.849	1274.8	90.2	5.51	0.28
8285.8	2.81	1276.9	90.3	5.53	0.29
8293.3	2.775	1279.8	90.3	5.55	0.29
8300.9	2.735	1282	90.3	5.51	0.29
8308.4	2.702	1284.2	90.4	5.53	0.3
8316	2.662	1287	90.4	5.54	0.3
8323.5	2.628	1289.2	90.4	5.53	0.3
8331	2.587	1291.4	90.5	5.5	0.3
8338.5	2.548	1296.5	90.6	5.47	0.27
8361.2	2.44	1301.6	90.7	5.47	0.27
8368.6	2.401	1303.8	90.7	5.47	0.27
8376.2	2.367	1307.4	90.7	5.48	0.27
8391	2.293	1311.1	90.8	5.45	0.27
8398.6	2.254	1312.5	90.8	5.43	0.27
8406.1	2.222	1315.7	90.9	5.45	0.3
8413.7	2.181	1317.8	90.9	5.5	0.24
8421.2	2.148	1320.7	91	5.48	0.22
8428.7	2.108	1322.9	91	5.43	0.24

Table A1. continued.

Time (s)	Altitude (km)	Pressure (Pa)	Temperature (K)	CH ₄ (%)	1- σ (%)
8436.2	2.073	1325.1	91	5.47	0.25
8443.8	2.034	1328.1	91.1	5.45	0.24
8451.3	1.999	1331.1	91.1	5.42	0.25
8458.8	1.959	1333.3	91.2	5.43	0.25
8466.3	1.926	1337.7	91.3	5.44	0.24
8489	1.814	1343.8	91.4	5.41	0.26
8496.5	1.78	1345.3	91.4	5.42	0.25
8504	1.741	1347.5	91.4	5.44	0.25
8511.5	1.708	1350.4	91.5	5.43	0.25
8519.1	1.669	1352.6	91.5	5.44	0.25
8526.6	1.631	1354.8	91.6	5.45	0.24
8534.1	1.597	1357.7	91.6	5.4	0.2
8541.6	1.558	1360	91.7	5.42	0.23
8549.2	1.525	1362.2	91.7	5.42	0.23
8556.7	1.488	1364.4	91.8	5.45	0.21
8564.3	1.454	1366.6	91.8	5.43	0.19
8571.7	1.415	1369.7	91.9	5.46	0.22
8579.3	1.381	1371.9	91.9	5.49	0.21
8586.8	1.342	1376.4	92	5.48	0.22
8609.4	1.234	1381.7	92.1	5.47	0.22
8616.9	1.196	1385.7	92.2	5.52	0.21
8624.5	1.161	1387.2	92.2	5.51	0.21
8632	1.121	1389.5	92.2	5.5	0.21
8639.5	1.083	1392.5	92.3	5.5	0.21
8647	1.049	1394.9	92.3	5.49	0.22
8654.6	1.011	1397.1	92.4	5.53	0.26
8662.1	0.976	1400.1	92.4	5.54	0.25
8669.7	0.94	1402.3	92.4	5.51	0.22
8677.2	0.906	1404.6	92.5	5.49	0.25
8684.7	0.867	1409.2	92.5	5.47	0.26
8703.3	0.781	1414.8	92.6	5.46	0.26
8710.8	0.741	1416.3	92.6	5.43	0.23
8718.4	0.708	1420.8	92.7	5.42	0.23
8740.9	0.599	1426.2	92.8	5.42	0.23
8748.5	0.565	1429.3	92.9	5.43	0.23
8756	0.527	1431.5	92.9	5.41	0.21
8763.5	0.49	1433.8	92.9	5.42	0.21
8771	0.457	1436.1	93	5.41	0.22
8778.6	0.419	1438.4	93	5.39	0.22
8786.1	0.387	1441.4	93	5.41	0.22
8793.7	0.349	1443.7	93.1	5.37	0.15
8801.2	0.316	1446	93.1	5.36	0.15
8808.7	0.279	1448.2	93.1	5.37	0.15
8816.2	0.247	1450.5	93.2	5.39	0.13
8823.8	0.209	1453.7	93.2	5.4	0.13
8831.3	0.175	1457	93.3	5.41	0.13
8838.8	0.137	1460.9	93.4	5.4	0.13
8861.4	0.034	1465.5	93.4	5.39	0.14
8869	0.004	1466.5	93.5	5.4	0.14
8876.4	0	1466.5	93.5	5.4	0.15

Notes. First column is the time since beginning of GCMS measurements. Column 2, 3 and 4 are the altitude, atmospheric pressure and temperature, respectively, from HASI measurements for the corresponding time stamp. Column 5 and 6 are the retrieved methane mole fraction and its standard deviation. For altitudes comprised between 146 and 30 km, data has been binned to a kilometric resolution to enhance S/N. The associated values for time, altitude, pressure and temperature correspond to the average value of the bin in the GCMS and HASI data. Associated methane mole fraction corresponds to the retrieved value for the binned data. From 30 km and below, we used the native GCMS vertical resolution. In this range, timestamps correspond to the exact time of each measurement according to GCMS clock. Corresponding altitude, pressure and temperature were calculated using a linear interpolation between the two nearest HASI points. Reported methane mole fractions and uncertainties correspond to the retrieved values for each altitude smoothed using a 10 points moving median.

Table A2.
Initial fragmentation database used for the mass spectra decomposition.

	H ₂	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₂	HCN	N ₂	C ₂ H ₄	C ₂ H ₆	Ar	CO ₂	Ne
σ_j^{70}	1.021	3.524	4.374	3.442	2.508	5.115	6.422	2.769	3.1	0.513
$1/\sqrt{M_j}$	0.707	0.250	0.196	0.193	0.189	0.189	0.183	0.158	0.151	0.224
m/z 1	100.00	0.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 2	100.00	0.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 3	1.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 7	-	-	-	-	0.01	-	-	-	-	-
" 8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 12	-	0.60	0.54	0.69	-	3.81	0.12	-	0.50	-
" 13	-	1.87	2.59	0.32	-	0.70	0.27	-	-	-
" 14	-	5.06	0.14	0.23	4.67	1.95	1.61	-	-	-
" 15	-	71.74	-	-	0.03	0.22	2.54	-	-	-
" 16	-	100.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.18	-
" 17	-	1.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.04	-	100.00
" 21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.84	-
" 23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 24	-	-	4.08	-	-	1.81	0.36	-	-	-
" 25	-	-	17.40	-	-	6.33	2.25	-	-	-
" 26	-	-	100.00	2.07	-	45.98	17.10	-	-	-
" 27	-	-	2.09	100.00	0.64	54.4	27.72	-	-	-
" 28	-	-	-	0.57	100	100.00	100	-	6.77	-
" 29	-	-	-	-	1.25	2.11	24.69	-	-	-
" 30	-	-	-	-	0.02	-	34.01	-	-	-
" 31	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.75	-	-	-
" 32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.16	-
" 33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 36	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.33	-	-
" 37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.00	-	-
" 41	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 42	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 43	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 44	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.00	-
" 45	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.14	-
" 46	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.38	-
" 47	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 49	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
" 50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Notes. σ_j^{70} (in Å²) corresponds to the ionization cross section at 70 eV for the species j, as determined by the BEB method. This factor is used to correct for the differential ionization of molecules in the ion source. $1/\sqrt{M_j}$ (in u^{-1/2}) corresponds to the inverse of the square root of the mono-isotopic molecular mass of the species j, and is used to correct for the differential transfer of the species during sampling and due to the molecular flow occurring in the capillaries.